

PHYSIOLOGICAL PROFILE OF TRADITIONAL GAMES

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Abstract:

Competition plays a vital role in today's modern era where records are being practically rewritten and are being excelled mostly in every successive competition. To achieve something in the high level competition one must undergo continuous and systematic plan of training right from childhood. Kabaddi and wrestling is basically a team game played in the tropical countries of Asia. These indigenous game of India were adopted by other countries in Asia viz, Pakistan, Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh, srilanka, Maldives, Malaysia and many more. The main purpose of this study was to compare the physiological profiles such Blood pressure and Vital capacity of inter University Kabaddi and wrestling male players. To achieve the purpose of the study data was collected from one hundred and twenty players, sixty from each game, who have represented Karnataka state in particular game. The age of the subjects were ranging from 18-25 years. The data collected was treated with the statistical technique 't' and found there is a significant difference in the selected physiological aspects between Kabaddi and wrestling male players.

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Key Words: Physiology, Kabaddi, Wrestling, Blood Pressure, VitalCapacity.

INTRODUCTION:

People have been playing sporting games in one form or another since antiquity. Sporting events appears in earliest mythology and athletes were major celebrities in ancient Greece. Over the centuries, crowds have gathered to watch sporting competition with sometimes violent and nationalistic outcomes.

Aspirations and expectations of the people pertaining to the performance of sportsmen all over the world are going higher and higher. High level of performance by sportsmen and require a highly scientific approach and it should be done right from the level of identifying talents.

The physiological variables play an important role for the attainment of high level sports performance. Physiological variables may be defined as those variables, which are directly linked with

various physiological systems like heart rate, blood pressure, vital capacity, respiratory rate and hemoglobin. Physiological variables like cardiovascular efficiency, percentage of fat, reaction time, vital capacity and other should be taken into consideration. Cardio-respiratory endurance denoted capacity of individual to work effectively with the help of oxygen which is collected, transported and utilized by lungs, blood and muscles respectively. Any work as daily task or form of physical activity is directly related to energy supplying system which in turn is the cardio-respiratory endurance. The high intensity bouts of exercise, coupled with the total duration of the match, requires players to have well-developed aerobic and anaerobic a lactic (ATP-CP) energy systems.

Records and outstanding sporting achievement requires the highest standard of performance and maximum will power to achieve that standard. The limits of physiological performance are being consistently advanced through training and competition. Evaluation and analysis of world championships, Olympic games etc., indicate that only those athletes will achieve impressive performance who are suited for the sports in question, who possess the necessary moral characteristics, who have an outstanding physiological potential who have perfect command of the techniques and tactics of their sports and who have proved themselves over a number of years of competition. Soft ball and cricket is an outstanding game throughout the world. It is the most popular games.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY:

The main purpose of this study was to compare the physiological variables such as Blood pressure and Vital capacity of interuniversity kabaddi and wrestling players of Karnataka state university.

METHODOLOGY:

To achieve the purpose of the study data was collected from one hundred and twenty players, sixty each from Kabaddi and Wrestling game, who have represented university in Karnataka state. Subjects were randomly selected during tournaments. The age of the subjects were ranging from 18-25 years.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE:

The collected data was analyzed by using statistical technique 't' test with the help of 20th version of SPSS.

RESULTS:

To achieve the purpose of the study that data collected were put to statistical treatment and results are presented in the following tables.

Table 1a. Mean, standard deviation and 't' value of systolic blood pressure between Kabaddi and wrestling players

Sr. No.	Players	Sample Size	Mean value	Standard deviation	't' value
1.	Kabaddi	60	118.13	5.55	0.49
2.	wrestling	60	117.75	3.57	

*significant at 0.05 level.

The data obtained from the table reveals that, there was no significant difference in systolic blood pressure between Kabaddi and wrestling players. Because, the calculated 't' value 0.49 and which is lesser than the table value 1.96.

Table 1b. Mean, standard deviation and 't' value of diastolic blood pressure between Kabaddi and wrestling players

Sr. No.	Players	Sample Size	Mean value	Standard deviation	't' value
1.	Kabaddi	60	85.48	5.99	0.47
2.	wrestling	60	85.23	4.90	

*significant at 0.05 level.

The data presented in the table shows that there was no significant difference in diastolic blood pressure between Kabaddi and wrestling players. Both the players are having similar mean values in this component.

Table 2. Mean, standard deviation and 't' value of vital capacity between Kabaddi and Wrestling players

Sr. No.	Players	Sample Size	Mean value	Standard deviation	't' value
1.	Kabaddi	60	3.73	0.50	3.39*
2.	Wrestling	60	3.87	0.46	

*significant at 0.05 level.

The above table depicts the mean value, standard deviation and 't' value of vital capacity. There was significant difference in vital capacity between Kabaddi and wrestling players. Kabaddi players are having good vital capacity than wrestling players.

FINDINGS:

The above result shows that there is a significant difference in the selected physiological aspects such as blood pressure and vital capacity respectively.

In blood pressure (systolic & diastolic), the data obtained from the table reveals that, there was no significant difference in systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure between Kabaddi and wrestling players. Because, the calculated 't' values which is lesser than the table value 1.96. Hence, it is not significant at 0.05 level. So null hypothesis was accepted.

There was significant difference in vital capacity between Kabaddi and wrestling players.

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